

Selective CO₂ adsorption over alkali metal cation-exchanged UZM-9 zeolites

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ABSTRACT

Adsorption on zeolites reduces CO₂ emissions and cuts the energy costs of processing gas mixtures, such as natural gas, biogas, and landfill gas (CO₂/CH₄ of various concentrations). Among zeolite frameworks, LTA stands out for its CO₂ adsorption and/or separation potential, particularly the Na-LTA zeolite with a Si/Al ratio of ~5. However, the impact of different cations on the separation efficiency of this system remains unknown. In this study, we tested various alkali-metal-exchanged UZM-9 zeolites (Si/Al = 4.5) for their selective adsorption of CO₂ over CH₄. K⁺-exchanged UZM-9 reached the highest CO₂ affinity, isosteric heat of adsorption, and selectivity, outperforming more commonly used Na⁺ forms. This enhanced performance likely stems from the predominant location of K⁺ in the 8-ring window, which fosters strong CO₂ interactions, potentially via bridging CO₂ species. Due to partial pore blocking, the total uptake may decrease slightly, but the K-UZM-9 system effectively balances CO₂/CH₄ selectivity and adsorption capacity. Therefore, K-UZM-9 emerges as a promising adsorbent for energy-efficient gas separation and carbon capture applications.

1. Introduction

Adsorption is a key technology in ongoing efforts to reduce CO₂ emissions and to cut costs of conventional, energy-intensive CO₂ capture and separation procedures, such as distillation or amine scrubbing [1–6]. Currently, various industrial processes rely on CO₂ adsorption for large-scale applications, such as fuel production [2], NH₃ synthesis, and post-combustion CO₂ capture [5,7]. But zeolitic materials may advance industrial-scale applications of CO₂ adsorption [1,3,8] thanks to their relatively low price, high physicochemical stability, and characteristic structures. These inorganic (typically aluminosilicate) crystalline materials feature a porous framework of interconnected channels and/or cavities with dimensions comparable to those of common small gas molecules, such as CO₂ or light hydrocarbons. This framework usually contains extra-framework cations, which compensate for its negative charge, resulting from the trivalent cations in the framework. Broadly speaking, the combined properties of the zeolite framework (topology, framework density, pore volume, and pore opening size) and the extra-framework cations (size, charge, and localization) govern the

adsorption process [9].

Among the most promising zeolite frameworks for CO₂ adsorption and/or separation, LTA (see Fig. 1a) holds the highest potential for energy-efficient CO₂ isolation from mixtures with other gases, such as CH₄ (natural gas/biogas/landfill gas), but also for example N₂ (flue gas), or CO/H₂ (syngas) [10–16]. LTA zeolites have been intensely investigated [17–19] for their affordability and straightforward synthesis (when Si/Al = 1), combined with their highly desirable attributes (adsorption capacity, regenerability, and CO₂ selectivity), which explain why they outperform many other zeolite frameworks, such as FAU and CHA [1]. The LTA pore system consists of large cages interconnected by relatively narrow, 8-ring windows, forming a structure with a very high pore volume. At 14.2 T-atoms per 1000 Å³, its density ranks among the lowest of all zeolitic frameworks. Moreover, the LTA is divided by “bottleneck” chokepoints, approximately 4.1 Å in diameter, which restrict access to large species unable to diffuse through the framework.

The ability of guest species to diffuse through the 8-rings can be further limited by extra-framework cations, although they are usually located in other areas of the LTA pore system, depending on the cation

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type (see Fig. 1b). It has been reported for the low-silica (Si/Al = 1 – 1.5) LTA that extra-framework cations can be coordinated above 6-rings (site S1), inside the 8-ring pore entrance (site S2), or above 4-rings (site S3) [14,20–22]. Smaller cations like Li⁺ are often found in the S3 and S1 sites [22], whereas larger cations like Na⁺ occupy mainly S1 sites, with a small fraction (of up to 25 %) coordinated in 8-rings (S2 sites). In turn, K⁺ cations are predominantly located in the middle of the 8-ring window (the S2 site) [21]. These differences in cation location account for differences in charge compensation and, as a result, in the strength of the respective active sites. Furthermore, the concentration of extra-framework cations in S2 sites can reduce the accessibility of gas molecules to the pore system due to gate and molecular-trapdoor effects. The gate effect derives from steric hindrance induced by extra-framework cations in the pore entrance. The molecular-trapdoor effect refers to the selective ability of a guest molecule to bypass an obstructing extra-framework cation inside the entrance window. Both phenomena can be exploited for highly efficient gas separations [10,11, 23,24].

As described above, zeolites with very low Si/Al ratios ($\rightarrow 1$) may markedly increase CO₂ selectivity through steric hindrance or kinetic restriction. However, such a high concentration of framework aluminum and extra-framework cations will likely increase the CO₂ interaction energy significantly (upon CO₂ chemisorption and/or interactions with multiple cations at once), so the cost of regenerating these adsorbents may increase accordingly [14]. Nevertheless, Na-LTA zeolites with a Si/Al ratio of approximately 5 balance working capacity and CO₂/CH₄ separation selectivity, as shown by García et al. [25], using the Ruthven statistical model [26]. Yet, the effect of different cations on the separation efficiency of this system remains unknown despite their key role in adsorption. By unraveling interactions between cations and LTA zeolites, we may leverage their effect to optimize the compromise between capacity, selectivity, and regenerability (adsorption heat) in CO₂ capture applications.

In this study, we aimed to assess the effect of various cations on LTA zeolite adsorption. For this purpose, we synthesized UZM-9 zeolite (Si/Al = 4.5), with an LTA framework topology, and exchanged it into Li⁺, Na⁺, and K⁺ cationic forms. These cations (specifically Na⁺ and K⁺) were selected specifically for their low charge (which results in a large quantity of cations – active sites – required to compensate the negative charge of the zeolite framework), low price (in the case of Na⁺ and K⁺), chemically inert, and environmentally benign character. The obtained materials were tested for CO₂ and CH₄ adsorption in both single-gas volumetric and co-adsorption chromatographic experiments. In addition, *in-situ* FTIR measurements of adsorbed CO₂ species provided deeper insights into the underlying mechanism of these interactions. Combined, our findings demonstrate that the K-UZM-9 system provides optimal CO₂/CH₄ selectivity and adsorption capacity, potentially spurring energy-efficient carbon capture applications.

2. Results and discussion

The parent UZM-9 material (in proton form) and the individual cationic forms were characterized by PXRD, N₂ adsorption, SEM, MAS NMR, and ICP-MS. The PXRD patterns (Fig. 1d) of as-synthesized, calcined, and ion-exchanged zeolites matched those reported in the literature [27–30], showing all the characteristic diffraction lines. Neither calcination nor ion-exchange significantly changed the diffractograms, confirming that the structure is preserved during the post-synthesis treatment.

SEM images (Fig. 1c) of the parent UZM-9 zeolite showed regular, cubic crystals averaging 1 μm and forming larger aggregates with many edges, resembling corners of intertwined cubes. These observations corroborate previously published data on UZM-9 materials [28,30].

Table 1 summarizes the cation-to-aluminum ratios of the UZM-9 samples under study, and the textural properties determined by N₂ physisorption at 77.3 K. All these materials have a Si/Al ratio of

Fig. 1. Alkali Cations Occupy Distinct Framework Sites and Modulate Pore Accessibility in UZM-9. (a) Schematic representation of the LTA framework topology. (b) The location of extra-framework sites within the LTA cage is highlighted in different colors (yellow = S1, purple = S2, and green = S3). (c) The PXRD patterns of the as-made, calcined, and ion-exchanged UZM-9 zeolites. (d) The SEM images of the parent UZM-9 zeolite. (e) The N₂ adsorption (●) / desorption (○) isotherms at 77.3 K of the parent, Li, Na, and K-UZM-9 zeolites.

Table 1

The degree of ion-exchange and textural properties (from N₂ adsorption) of the parent UZM-9 zeolite and its alkali ion-exchanged daughter materials.

Sample	M/Al	S _{BET} ^a (m ² /g)	S _{ex} ^b (m ² /g)	V _{mic} ^b (cm ³ /g)	V _{tot} ^c (cm ³ /g)
Parent UZM-9	0.05 ^a	642	30.4	0.27	0.32
Li-UZM-9	0.88	641	32.1	0.27	0.32
Na-UZM-9	0.84	347	16.5	0.13	0.16
K-UZM-9	0.87	66	11.1	0.02	0.04

^a – M stands for Na⁺

^b – determined from the t-plot using the Harkins-Jura thickness equation [31]

^c – based on the Gurvich rule [31], V_{tot} determined from the amount adsorbed at p/p₀ = 0.95

approximately 4.5, with an ion exchange degree ranging from 84 % to 88 %, as shown by chemical analysis. The incomplete ion-exchange was mostly attributed to the existence of some difficult-to-exchange extra-framework protons. This was evidenced by the ²⁷Al MAS NMR experiments of the parent UZM-9, which revealed the presence of tetrahedrally coordinated Al (i.e. coordinated in the framework) without any observable quantity of penta- or hexa-coordinated Al sites (i.e. extra-framework). (see Fig. S1, left panel). These residual extra-framework protons were confirmed by *in-situ* FTIR measurements of pre-treated samples (see Fig. S2), whose O–H signals characteristic of Brønsted acidic species, typically found in the range from 3550 to 3650 cm⁻¹, were clearly visible in the FTIR spectra. Their intensity correlated with the degree of ion-exchange, as determined by ICP-MS (see Table 1).

N₂ adsorption/desorption isotherms at 77.3 K (Fig. 1e) differed significantly between samples. The adsorption isotherm of Li-UZM-9 was nearly identical to that of the parent material (corresponding to a micropore volume of approximately 0.27 cm³/g). In contrast, the Na-UZM-9 and K-UZM-9 micropore volume accessible to the dinitrogen was reduced to approximately half (0.12 cm³/g) and to almost zero (0.02 cm³/g), respectively (see Table 1). This decrease in accessible micropore volume most likely results from kinetic blocking (gate effect) of the N₂ molecule caused by the extra-framework cations in the 8-ring pore entrance, as commonly observed in low-silica zeolites [23].

Complete hindrance of mass transport into the pore system requires

100 % occupancy of the 8-rings by a bulkier cation, corresponding to three cations in this site per unit cell of the LTA framework. Considering that UZM-9 statistically contains 3.7 – 3.8 extra-framework cations per unit cell, as per our chemical analysis (see Table 1) and that K⁺ cations predominantly occupy 8-ring pore entrances in low-silica LTA materials (Si/Al = 1.5) [21], this near-zeroing of the accessible micropore volume aligns with published data. In Na-UZM-9, only a fraction of the extra-framework cations should be coordinated at the 8-ring site [20], thus only partly blocking the pore system. In Li-UZM-9, conversely, the cations should not be coordinated at the 8-ring site; even for Si/Al = 1, the experimental occupancy of the 8-ring window is only approximately 33 %, according to literature [22]. This result is in line with the zero decrease in accessible micropore volume.

Single-gas CO₂ and CH₄ adsorption isotherms recorded at 293 K (see Figs. 2a and 2b) and their isosteric adsorption heats (see Figs. 2c and 2d), calculated from sets of isotherms measured at 273, 293 and 313 K, as well as 333 K for CH₄ (see Figs. S5-S6 in SI), demonstrate that the type of extra-framework cations has a strong effect on zeolite adsorption.

The adsorption isotherms of CO₂ (Fig. 2a) show a nonlinear, concave shape, which is typical of strong interactions between CO₂ molecules and extra-framework cations [1,8]. In the lower pressure range of pressures (0 – 50 torr), CO₂ uptake increased in the following order: Li⁺ < Na⁺ < K⁺. The CO₂ uptake of K-UZM-9 was significantly higher than that of the other two samples. Concurrently, the zero-coverage adsorption heat (~38 kJ/mol) of K-UZM-9 was also higher than that of the other two adsorbents (34.5 kJ/mol) (Fig. 2c). At higher pressures (→ 1 atm), though, the increasing order of CO₂ uptake was K⁺ < Na⁺ < Li⁺. This order correlated with the pore volume available, as bulkier cations occupy more space and, therefore, decrease the uptake.

Under the same conditions, CH₄ adsorption (Fig. 2b) was significantly lower than CO₂ adsorption because CH₄ interacts with the zeolite and its cations much more weakly, as it possesses neither dipole nor quadrupole moment, whereas CO₂ boasts a strong quadrupole moment. Unlike CO₂, the isosteric heats of CH₄ measured on M-UZM-9 zeolites (Fig. 2d) differed only slightly as a function of individual extra-framework cationic forms and uptake. For all three materials, the uptake values ranged from 17.0 to 17.7 kJ/mol.

No steric restrictions (conductive to gate or molecular trapdoor

Fig. 2. K⁺ Cations Strengthen CO₂–Zeolite Interactions and Increase Adsorption Heat. CO₂ (a) and CH₄ (b) adsorption isotherms of M-UZM-9 zeolites at 293 K. Isosteric adsorption heats of CO₂ (c) and CH₄ (d) on M-UZM-9 zeolites.

effects) were observed in any UZM-9 sample for CO₂ or CH₄ at 273 – 333 K, given the lack of features typically of this phenomenon, such as sigmoidal adsorption isotherms [32] and unexpected uptake decreases at lower temperatures [24]. The absence of these effects contrasts with our observations for N₂ at 77.3 K. This difference is likely due to 1) the higher temperature of the experiment, and 2) the stronger electric field generated by the adsorbate [24]. Our results, furthermore, differ from the results reported by Sun et al., who discussed in detail the CO₂/N₂ separation efficacy of Na⁺- and K⁺-exchanged LTA zeolites with lower Si/Al ratios (1 – 2.2). These authors demonstrated that K-LTA materials (with Si/Al up to 2.2) present kinetic restrictions for CO₂ and N₂ transport, suggesting that the “molecular trapdoor effect” [23,24] accounts for the observed behavior. Notwithstanding their careful analysis, the difference between our observations and theirs may be explained by differences in the Si/Al ratios of the zeolites, as our zeolites contained approximately 3 – 4 extra-framework cations per unit cell, whereas theirs housed over 7 cations per unit cell. Further supporting our argument, adsorption isotherms of the Na-UZM-9 material (with Si/Al = 4.5) corroborated data from the literature. Both our CO₂ and CH₄ uptake values and our zero-coverage adsorption heats of Na-UZM-9 are in line with values previously reported for Na-LTA-3.5 and Na-LTA-5 by Palomino et al. [12].

To gain deeper insights into the CO₂ adsorption process, we performed in-situ FTIR measurements (under an equilibrium pressure of 0.8 torr) to investigate the regions characteristic of carbonates (Fig. 3a) and the ν_3 vibration region of CO₂ (Fig. 3b). Although the CO₂ ν_1 symmetric stretching vibration is normally inactive in IR measurements, this vibration is observed at 1382 cm⁻¹ in the spectrum of Li- and Na-UZM-9 materials due to the distortion of the CO₂ symmetry upon interaction with the extra-framework cation. In Li-UZM-9, a clear band is also visible at 1651 cm⁻¹, most likely corresponding to an unspecified carbonate species. By contrast, K-UZM-9 shows two strong signals at 1325 and 1680 cm⁻¹, matching the results of K-FAU (Si/Al ~ 2.5) [33] and K-CHA (Si/Al ~ 2.2) [34]. Some authors [34] have assigned this pair of

signals to bidentate carbonates. But while K-UZM-9 may form carbonate species, these signals are nevertheless weak. Therefore, chemisorption should not have a strong effect on the adsorption process as a whole.

The ν_3 asymmetric vibration region (2300 – 2400 cm⁻¹) includes several strong signals in the case of each of the cationic forms. The spectrum time-lapse of Na-UZM-9 upon desorption (Fig. 3d) shows three clear signals, namely the main, albeit the least stable, signal at 2353 cm⁻¹, a large shoulder at 2361 cm⁻¹, and a weak, but stable, shoulder at 2345 cm⁻¹. The band at 2353 cm⁻¹ can be assigned to CO₂ interacting with a single Na⁺ cation based on frequencies reported for similar systems (2356 cm⁻¹ for Na-MFI [35], 2354 cm⁻¹ for Na-FAU [33,36–38], and 2352 cm⁻¹ for Na-FER [39]). The high-frequency (2361 cm⁻¹) shoulder has been previously observed in Na-LTA [10,14, 40–42] and assigned to a bridging CO₂ species, coordinated between a cation in an 8-ring (S2 site) and an adjacent cation in a 6-ring (S1 site) [10,14,40–42]. The stable low-frequency shoulder (2344 cm⁻¹) has been identified in Na-LTA (Si/Al = 1) [40,42], as well as other systems (MFI [35], FAU [33,36,38]), and ascribed to either a different type of bridging-CO₂ complex (in FAU) or interactions with a less exposed single Na⁺ cation (in MFI). The signals observed in the time-lapse spectrum of Li-UZM-9 upon desorption (Fig. 3c) somewhat resemble those observed in Na⁺, but their interpretation based on previously published data is not completely clear yet. In both the case of Na⁺ and Li⁺, 10 min of desorption at ambient conditions was sufficient for desorption of over 95 % of the physisorbed CO₂.

CO₂ adsorption on K-UZM-9 yielded only a single band centered around 2351 cm⁻¹, several times stronger than the bands observed in the other two materials, with a weak and less stable shoulder around 2338 cm⁻¹. The physisorbed species were overall more stable than in the case of Na⁺ and Li⁺, but their intensity nonetheless decreased by 95 % in about 13 min of desorption. Such spectra, with the main band around 2346 – 2351 cm⁻¹ and a shoulder around 2335 cm⁻¹, are typical of physisorbed CO₂ on K⁺-exchanged zeolites, such as K-LTL [43], K-MFI [35], K-FAU [33,38], and K-CHA [34]. In previous studies [33,

Fig. 3. Bridging CO₂ Complexes Form Preferentially on K⁺ Sites within 8-Rings. The normalized vibrational spectra of adsorbed CO₂ - the carbonate region (a), the ν_3 region (b), on Li- (black), Na- (red), and K-UZM-9 (green) zeolites. Time-lapse of the ν_3 region changes upon the desorption from $p_{\text{eq}} = 0.8$ torr (captured for ~ 15 min). (c) Li-UZM-9, (d) Na-UZM-9, (e) K-UZM-9.

38] on a related K-FAU system (Si/Al = 2.55), which also shows stronger CO₂ adsorption than Li- and Na-FAU systems, the authors ascribed this strong band to 1) the much higher concentration of bridging CO₂ complexes in K-FAU systems and to 2) the formation of adsorbed CO₂ species that simultaneously interact with the cation and the adjacent basic oxygens, whose basicity is less strongly offset when the cation is located in 8-rings.

The formation of bridging CO₂ complexes in Na- and K-LTA systems can be explained by geometrical factors, based on previously published data [14,20–22] on cation localization in the LTA system. For Na⁺ cations located in adjacent S1 and S2 sites (a possible, but likely not predominant arrangement, due to partial occupancy of the S2 sites), the typical intercationic distance is ~ 7 Å. This value is similar to the ideal intercationic distance for bridging CO₂ species (7.3 Å), as predicted computationally [9,14,33]. An even closer agreement between the typical intercationic distance observed in the zeolite and the distance required for bridging CO₂ species is found in K-UZM-9. In this material, two K⁺ cations in adjacent S2 sites (the predominant arrangement) are separated by ~8.4 Å, which is nearly equal to the distance of 8.3 Å that is ideal for bridging species. In Li-LTA systems, conversely, the intercationic distances characteristic of typical Li⁺ positioning are either too short (~5 Å, in the case of two Li⁺ cations localized in adjacent S1 and S3 sites) compared to the ideal value (6.5 Å) for the formation of the bridging complex, or, alternatively, too large (in the other arrangements). This makes the formation of bridging complexes in Li-UZM-9 unlikely. We conclude that the likely much more common formation of bridging CO₂ species on K-UZM-9 is the main reason for its stronger interaction with CO₂.

The potential and efficiency of adsorbents for separating gas mixtures are usually assessed based on their adsorption selectivity, which can be estimated from single gas adsorption data in various ways. The most common approaches include calculating the ratios of Henry's constants (the slopes of single gas isotherms at near-zero coverage) or applying the ideal adsorption solution theory (IAST), which simulates co-adsorption from single-gas adsorption isotherms (see SI for details). Table 2 summarizes data on the three zeolites under study and outlines select results from the literature on other LTA zeolites. Selectivity can be quantified from single-component adsorption (*vide supra*) and co-adsorption (*vide infra*) experiments. Fig. 4a shows the variation of IAST selectivity as a function of pressure. More specifically, selectivity was calculated using the IAST, assuming a 1:1 mixture of CO₂ and CH₄ and employing the Sips adsorption model [44] to describe the single-component adsorption data.

Both the slopes (Henry constants' ratios) and the IAST estimated across the pressure range (0 – 800 torr) indicate that K-UZM-9 is the most selective zeolite, reflecting the highest CO₂ adsorption heat. In all three adsorbents, IAST selectivity varied as a function of pressure, as expected for CO₂/CH₄ systems in alkali-metal exchanged zeolites – at low pressures, selectivity was relatively high due to highly selective interactions of CO₂ with available cationic sites. At higher pressures, the cationic sites become occupied, so additional CO₂ molecules are forced to form weaker geminal complexes with the cations or to interact primarily with the aluminosilicate framework or with other gas molecules (lateral interactions). This steep decrease is often followed by a slow increase, caused by the increasingly stronger effect of adsorbate-adsorbate (lateral) interactions as the pores fill up.

Na- and K-UZM-9 materials perform similarly, undergoing an approximately 50 – 60 % decrease in CO₂/CH₄ selectivity after the initial saturation of their cationic sites by CO₂ molecules, indicating surface heterogeneity. In Li-UZM-9, though, this initial decrease in selectivity is significantly smaller (only approximately 15 %), yielding results closer to those observed in materials without strong adsorption sites (such as H-exchanged zeolites). This result of Li-UZM-9 aligns with adsorption model fits (see Table S1), revealing near-Langmuir CO₂ adsorption isotherms, typical of materials with a homogenous surface.

To analyze CO₂/CH₄ co-adsorption and adsorptive separation under realistic conditions, we performed breakthrough experiments at 298 K under atmospheric pressure with an equimolar mixture (resembling the biogas/landfill gas composition) of CO₂ and CH₄ (see Figs. 4b, 4c, and 4d). CO₂ adsorbed more strongly than CH₄ on all cationic forms of the UZM-9 zeolite, with CH₄ breaking through immediately after the inert gas. In contrast, CO₂ breakthroughs were delayed by 160–180 s, depending on the type of extra-framework cation. These findings confirm our predictions from single-component adsorption isotherms. The breakthrough curves, particularly the breakthrough times and the composition of the outlet gas, enabled us to calculate the adsorbed amounts of both adsorbates and, therefore, CO₂/CH₄ selectivity (see Table 2).

All three sets of breakthrough curves are very similar, yielding comparable selectivity and gas uptake. Li and K-UZM-9 zeolites reached the highest CO₂ adsorption values, approximately 2.9 mmol/g, matching their single-component volumetric uptakes at 300 torr, 3.2 and 3.0 mmol/g, respectively. In turn, uptake on Na-UZM-9 was approximately 2.5 mmol/g, with 2.7 mmol/g from the adsorption isotherm at 300 torr. Methane uptake ranged from 0.5 to 0.6 mmol/g, values that were considerably higher than those calculated from the single-

Table 2
Summary of CO₂ and CH₄ adsorption on various completely ion-exchanged and electroneutral LTA frameworks.

Sample	Si/Al	n _{CO₂} , 1 atm (mmol/g)	n _{CH₄} , 1 atm (mmol/g)	S _{CO₂/CH₄} ^a (-)	zero coverage CO ₂ heat ^b (kJ/mol)	Source
Li-UZM-9	4.5	4.33 ^[293 K]	0.42 ^[293 K]	4.8 ^[BTC, 298 K] 64 ^[slopes, 293 K] 58 ^[IAST, 293 K]	34.5	This work
Na-UZM-9	4.5	3.81 ^[293 K]	0.44 ^[293 K]	4.5 ^[BTC, 298 K] 94 ^[slopes, 293 K] 63 ^[IAST, 293 K]	34.5	This work
K-UZM-9	4.5	3.58 ^[293 K]	0.55 ^[293 K]	6.0 ^[BTC, 298 K] 132 ^[slopes, 293 K] 80 ^[IAST, 293 K]	38	This work
AlPO-42	-	1.02 ^[303 K]		6 ^[BTC, 5 atm, 303 K]		[25]
ITQ-29	∞	1.02 ^[303 K]	0.25 ^[303 K]	3.5 ^[slopes, 303 K]	20.7	[12]
Na-LTA	5.0	3.07 ^[303 K]	0.33 ^[303 K]	20 ^[BTC, 5 atm, 303 K] 52.6 ^[slopes, 303 K]	33.2	[12,25]
Na-LTA	3.5	4.64 ^[303 K]	0.44 ^[303 K]	19 ^[BTC, 5 atm, 303 K] 111.5 ^[slopes, 303 K]	34.8	[12,25]
Na-LTA	1.9	5.07 ^[303 K]	0.47 ^[303 K]	306 ^[BTC, 5 atm, 303 K] 325.7 ^[slopes, 303 K]	43.2	[12,25]
Na-A	1.0	4.19 ^[303 K]	1.37 ^[303 K]	1270.6 ^[slopes, 303 K]	48.9	[12]

^a – The calculated selectivity values are expressed either as the ratio of zero-coverage slopes or IAST selectivity for a 1:1 mixture at 1 atm.

^b – The adsorption heat of CO₂ is calculated using the isosteric method

Fig. 4. K⁺ Exchange Maximizes CO₂/CH₄ Selectivity under Both Equilibrium and Dynamic Conditions. (a) The CO₂/CH₄ selectivity on the UZM-9 zeolites (Li⁺ = black, Na⁺ = red, K⁺ = green) calculated by the IAST (CO₂:CH₄ = 1:1, T = 293 K, Sips model employed). (b-d) Breakthrough curve measurements - the flows of CO₂ (red) and CH₄ (black) on the detector over time on Li-UZM-9 (b), Na-UZM-9 (c), and K-UZM-9 (d) zeolites.

component adsorption isotherm. The highest experimental CO₂/CH₄ selectivity (6.1) was observed in K-UZM-9, while Li-UZM-9 and Na-UZM-9 reached 4.8 and 4.4 selectivity, respectively. Qualitatively, these results align with those calculated from single-component adsorption isotherms (see Table 2). The large discrepancy between absolute values derived from adsorption isotherms and from breakthrough curve experiments was caused by the difference between the real and the ideal behavior of both adsorbates. Furthermore, the nearly simultaneous breakthrough of CH₄ and the inert marker used to determine the total gas flow introduced a systematic error to the calculation of methane uptake, which was significantly overestimated, thereby affecting the resulting values of methane uptake.

Broadly speaking, our Na-UZM-9 results corroborate findings previously published in the literature (see references in Table 2). Across all available criteria (CO₂ and CH₄ adsorption capacity, heat, and selectivity), the experimental data on Na-UZM-9 (Si/Al = 4.5) are in line with the results reported by Palomino et al. [12]

Completely (or nearly completely) ion-exchanged K-LTA zeolites (Si/Al > 3) had not been tested for CO₂/CH₄ adsorptive separation yet. Our results indicate that using K⁺ in LTA zeolites instead of Na⁺ enhances their selectivity for CO₂/CH₄ separation at the cost of a small decrease in adsorption capacity and a small increase in adsorption heat (implying slightly higher regeneration costs). Furthermore, the results of lower-silica (Si/Al = 1 – 2.8), partly exchanged K/Na-LTA zeolites published by Cheung et al. [10,11] indicate that K⁺ cations can markedly increase the adsorption selectivity of similar CO₂/N₂ systems due to the kinetic blocking/gate effect.

In conclusion, of the three materials, K-UZM-9 clearly exhibits the strongest and most selective interaction with CO₂, as evidenced by the steepness of the CO₂ adsorption isotherms, the CO₂/CH₄ selectivity obtained by various approaches, compensated by only a relatively modest increase in adsorption heat (~4 kJ/mol) and lower CO₂ capacity at higher pressure. The K-UZM-9 matches the performance of the most commonly used benchmark FAU zeolites, such as NaY and NaX. FAU materials may show a higher CO₂ adsorption capacity (~4.5 – 5.5 mmol/g, RT, 1 atm) than K-UZM-9 (~3.5 mmol/g) and a comparable or higher CO₂/CH₄ selectivity [45–47]. However, K-UZM-9 has a lower adsorption heat (38 vs. ~50 kJ/mol for NaX [47]). This parameter offers a major advantage by potentially decreasing the regeneration costs significantly.

3. Conclusions

This study provides valuable insights into CO₂ and CH₄ adsorption on alkali-metal-exchanged UZM-9 zeolites (LTA framework, Si/Al = 4.5). The type of extra-framework alkali cation (Li⁺, Na⁺, and K⁺) strongly affects CO₂ adsorption on UZM-9, with K⁺-exchanged UZM-9 exhibiting the highest CO₂ adsorption heat (~38 kJ/mol) and the steepest adsorption isotherm. K-UZM-9 also boasts the highest CO₂/CH₄ selectivity, rivaling that of the benchmark NaY zeolite in selectivity estimates from both single-component adsorption isotherms and co-adsorption experiments. Bridging CO₂ complexes and stronger interactions with the basic framework oxygens likely contribute to the enhanced CO₂ selectivity of K-UZM-9 as its K⁺ cations are predominantly found in 8-rings of the LTA framework. The enhanced adsorption capacity, adsorption heat, and CO₂/CH₄ selectivity of K-UZM-9 highlight its potential for CO₂ capture and gas upgrading through selective CO₂ removal. Considering its stability, tunability through ion exchange, and moderate synthesis conditions, K-UZM-9 stands out as a promising alternative to conventional adsorbents, particularly in energy-efficient separation processes. Overall, our findings may spur the development of advanced materials for CO₂ capture and natural gas upgrading by unveiling the role of the extra-framework alkali cation in adsorbent performance.

4. Experimental

The UZM-9 zeolite was synthesized following a hydrothermal procedure, as described in the literature [48]. For this purpose, 2.3 g of aluminum hydroxide was slowly dissolved under stirring in a mixture containing 20.0 g of an aqueous tetraethylammonium hydroxide solution (TEAOH, 35 wt%) and 16.4 g of an aqueous diethyldimethylammonium hydroxide solution (DEDMAOH, 20 wt%). Subsequently, 11.1 g of silica (ULTRASIL® VN 3) was added to the mixture, forming a dense white gel. A second mixture, consisting of 0.5 g of NaOH dissolved in 4.2 g of a tetramethylammonium (TMAOH) aqueous solution (25 wt%) and 9.8 g of water, was then added to the beaker with the stirred mixture. The synthesis was seeded at 0.5 wt% of the synthesis mixture weight and homogenized for 30 min. The gel was then transferred into a 90-mL Teflon-lined stainless-steel autoclave and heated at 423 K under agitation for two days. The molar composition of the synthesis gel was 1 SiO₂: 0.16 Al(OH)₃: 0.22 TEAOH: 0.15 DEDMAOH: 0.06 TMAOH: 0.06 NaOH: 11.2 H₂O. After the heating, the

autoclaves were cooled down with a stream of water, and the solid contents were washed with distilled water, centrifuged, and dried in an oven at 333 K overnight.

The as-made samples were calcined at 793 K for 6 h (heating ramp 1 K/min) under N₂ flow for the first two hours and then under air flow for the remaining four hours. The calcined materials were converted into corresponding alkali-metal cationic forms through fourfold ion-exchange with 100 mL of a 1.0 M solution of MNO₃ (M = Na, K) or LiCl, under stirring, at room temperature, for three hours per cycle. After each cycle, the samples were centrifuged, and the supernatant was decanted. After the final cycle, the samples were washed with water, centrifuged, decanted, and left to dry in the air.

The crystallinity of all the UZM-9 samples was assessed by powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD) on a Bruker AXS D8 Advance diffractometer equipped with a LYNXEYE XE-T energy-dispersive detector using Cu K α radiation in the Bragg-Brentano focusing geometry (in the 2 θ range from 3 to 40°). The crystal morphology of the UZM-9 samples without any sample coating was assessed under a scanning electron microscope (SEM, FEI Quanta 200 F microscope).

The chemical composition of the samples was determined by ICP-MS analysis (Agilent 7900 ICP-MS). To this end, 30 mg of sample was mixed with 1.8 mL of HNO₃ (67 – 69 %), 5.4 mL of HCl (34 – 37 %), and 1.8 mL of HF (47 – 51 %) in a Teflon vessel, placed into the microwave (Speedwave® XPERT, Berghof), and heated at 483 K (heating rate 5 K/min) for 25 min. After cooling down, the HF surplus was neutralized with 16 mL of a H₃BO₃ solution and further treatment in a microwave at 463 K (heating rate 5 K/min) for 10 min. Once cooled, the solutions were diluted with distilled water to a final volume of 50 mL for analysis.

The porosity and textural properties of the UZM-9 materials were evaluated by acquiring nitrogen adsorption/desorption isotherms at 77.3 K on a Micromeritics 3Flex static volumetric Surface Area Analyzer. The Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) method [31,49] was used to calculate the specific surface area (S_{BET}) with adsorption data in the range of relative pressures $p/p_0 = 0.02 - 0.10$. Micropore volume (V_{mic}) and external surface area (S_{ext}) were calculated using the t -plot method and the Harkins-Jura master isotherm model [31,50]. The adsorbed amount at the relative pressure $p/p_0 = 0.95$ reflects the total pore volume (V_{tot}).

Adsorption isotherms of CO₂ and CH₄ were measured using a Micromeritics ASAP 2020 Plus Physisorption volumetric/manometric device at 273, 293, 313, and 333 K in the pressure range of 0 – 800 torr. The adsorption equilibrium threshold was set to < 0.01 % pressure change on a 20-second interval. The temperature of the sample was controlled using a Peltier thermostat with a platinum sensor (accuracy ± 0.1 K). Before the first measurement, the samples (ca. 400 mg of dry sample) were calcined at 623 K for 8 h under dynamic vacuum. Before each subsequent adsorption measurement, the samples were subjected to a 6-hour treatment at 523 K. In all experiments, 99.997 % CH₄ and 99.9996 % CO₂ (both supplied by Linde) were used without further purification.

The isosteric heats of adsorption were calculated using the Clausius-Clapeyron equation [51], as implemented in the Heat of Adsorption (HOA) plugin of the software supplied with the device.

In-situ FTIR experiments were performed on a Nicolet iS50 FTIR spectrometer equipped with an MCT/D cryo-detector, which was connected to a home-made transmission setup. Prepared as self-supporting wafers (density of ~ 10 mg/cm²), the samples were calcined at 623 K for 3 h under dynamic vacuum. In each case, a spectrum of the empty IR cell (without the sample in the beam) was recorded as the background for all subsequent measurements. The spectrum of the freshly treated sample was recorded first, and then the apparatus was filled with 0.8 torr of CO₂. The dose was left to equilibrate for 20 min, at which point the spectrum of the sample was measured (32 scans at 1 cm⁻¹ resolution). To assess the relative stability of the CO₂ bands, time-resolved FTIR spectra were recorded upon subsequent evacuation of the apparatus. The spectra were subsequently normalized to the same quantity of the sample in the beam using the intensity of zeolite framework overtones

and combination modes as the internal standard (2060 – 1760 cm⁻¹) to compare band intensities.

The three breakthrough curve experiments (BTC) were performed with 500 mg of granulated wet sample (aggregate size 0.25 – 0.5 mm). Before all three experiments, a treatment of up to 623 K in He flow (10 mL/min) was performed for two hours at the final temperature. The BTC experiments were performed in 10 mL/min of feed consisting of 2 mL/min He (with a trace of Ne), 4 mL/min CH₄, and CO₂ (a 50:50 mixture) at 298 K. The Ne signal was used to determine the time it takes for the gas to pass the adsorbent without adsorption. Signal 15 was used for CH₄; signal 44, for CO₂; and signal 20 (for Ne), for He (for differentiation from the pure helium used in the treatment) after normalization.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.jcou.2025.103305](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcou.2025.103305).

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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